

What is a DOI? Digital Object Identifier

A DOI, or Digital Object Identifier, is one of a number of ways of making a permanent link to a given web location, a so-called “persistent identifier”. Web addresses (or URLs) may change as people reorganize their web servers, but a DOI is intended to always point to the given page or document, and therefore gives users a link that will work even when the underlying web page or document moves.

How can I use a DOI to find the document or page it refers to?

- If your DOI starts with `http://` or `https://`, simply paste it into your web browser. This will usually lead you directly to the relevant page or document.
- If your DOI starts with a number, however, then you need to add a prefix to find the web location. Older DOIs are often presented in this way and usually start with the number 10. You can turn any DOI into a URL by adding `http://doi.org/` before the DOI number. For example, the dataset with DOI “10.5281/zenodo.3369922” can be found by typing the following into your browser: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3369922>

If you wish to cite an item with a DOI, then you need only give the DOI code rather than the URL of the page.

DOIs are commonly used by journal publishers, academic book publishers, dataset archives, and others. If you submit an article or dataset to be published, then that publisher or service will usually assign a persistent identifier, like a DOI, to your item for you.

Occasionally you may find a DOI that will not resolve to the correct web page. The reason for this is usually that the organization that requested the DOI has not updated the registration in the DOI database. It is also possible that the DOI resolves to a page that is behind a subscription wall but this should be obvious to you when you land on the page and you should then contact your library for help.